

EFFECTS OF GLASS CEILING AND STEREOTYPIC LEADERSHIP STYLE ON THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIA'S MEDIA INDUSTRIES: THE CASE OF THE NIGERIAN TELEVISION AUTHORITY AND AFRICA INDEPENDENT TELEVISION

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of stereotypic media leadership style in NTA and AIT. It historicized the critical-cultural variables underpinning the exclusion of women in the appointment to executive positions such as the Director-General of the Nigeria's foremost media organizations; NTA and AIT. The study aims to examine how stereotypic media leadership affects career advancement and professional development of female media practitioners in NTA and AIT; explore the influence of socio-cultural norms on the perception of female journalists or practitioners' appointment as director-general in NTA and AIT; and identify the common leadership stereotypes encountered by female media practitioners in NTA and AIT. The study adopted the Glass Ceiling and Gender Role Theories, a Quantitative research method, an infinite population, and 20 available samples were purposively studied through a structured questionnaire. The results showed that stereotypic leadership inhibits women from achieving their career peaks and reduces inclusivity. Enforcing gender equity policies in media companies, offering leadership training programs for women, and creating mentorship opportunities in media organizations to review recruitment and promotion practices to ensure fairness and transparency in compliance with affirmative action should be encouraged.

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian media industry and its leadership (organizational) structures play important roles in contemporary society not only in agenda setting and shaping public opinion but also in influencing sociocultural norms and policies through content development, production, distribution, and consumption. These underpinnings are critical in media management and media functionality through leadership structure with a specific focus on the

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appointment of key management positions in the foremost public and private media organizations in Nigeria (Oliveira & Huang 2025).

Leadership is essential for setting editorial direction, ethical standards, and content dissemination within these media structures. However, media leadership is not always equitably distributed, especially across gender lines. Despite their growing presence in journalism and broadcasting, female practitioners remain significantly underrepresented in top-tier positions. This underrepresentation is not merely a statistical imbalance but reflects deep-rooted stereotypes and systemic gender biases that hinder women's advancement to leadership roles in the media. The topic of media organization leadership stereotype among female practitioners is particularly relevant in the context of Nigeria, where sociocultural norms, patriarchal structures and, institutional practices elongate gender inequality. Regardless of global progress in women's rights and increased participation in various professions, gender inequality remains a persistent issue in media leadership. Women working in media organizations continue to face structural, cultural and, interpersonal stereotypes that limit their advancement into decision-making and leadership roles. These stereotypes often manifest as biased assumptions about women's leadership capabilities, professional commitment, and work-life balance.

Arogundade (2010), explored the gendered dynamics of media leadership, highlighting the underrepresentation of women in decision-making roles within Nigerian newsrooms. He argues that this disparity is not necessarily due to a lack of competence among female journalists but, rather due to structural and cultural barriers rooted in patriarchal beliefs. These include the presumption that women are less authoritative or decisive, and assumptions about how their family responsibilities interfere with their professional duties. However, despite the increasing presence of women in journalism and media-related professions, men disproportionately fill leadership roles. This imbalance is often attributed to deeply entrenched gender stereotypes and structural barriers, societal expectations, and cultural norms that have long influenced gender roles, often downgrading women to subordinate positions both at home and in the workplace (Northouse, 2018; North, 2009; Mickinsey & Company, 2018). According to Okunna (1996), the Nigerian media industry reflects the male-controlled structure of society, which tends to undervalue women's contributions and leadership potential. Women are often perceived as incapable of handling the pressure and demands of leadership roles, especially in high-stakes and fast-paced sectors such as the media. This stereotype affects women's career progression and limits their access to mentorship, training opportunities, and networks that are crucial for leadership development (Kempton, 2025; Koenig, 2022; Lamer, et al.; 2025). Omenugha and Oji (2008) further emphasized that female journalists in Nigeria are often confined to "soft" news beats, such as lifestyle, fashion, and human interest stories, while the more prestigious beats such as politics, sports, and crime, are typically reserved for their male counterparts. This segregation not only reflects gender bias but also denies women the necessary exposure and experience to qualify for leadership roles. Institutional practices and newsroom cultures that subtly discourage female ambition or leadership aspirations reinforce these patterns.

The United Nations Economic, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2018) also draws attention to the global issue of gender inequality in media leadership, identifying a trend in which media organizations, regardless of geographic location, exhibit resistance to female leadership due to longstanding gender biases. This report underscores that women often have to work harder than their male counterparts to prove their competence and leadership capacity, a challenge that is even more pronounced in regions with strong patriarchal cultures. Nwabueze (2007) explained that media institutions often reflect societal norms, and where patriarchy is strong, as it is in many parts of Nigeria, they heavily influence employment dynamics, promotions, and leadership roles. Nwabueze emphasized that newsroom cultures often tolerate, or even endorse, gendered

expectations, where men are seen as natural leaders and women as followers or support staff. Obijiofor and Green (2001) argued that the positioning of women in African media structures is not just a matter of numbers but also of power and influence. In their view, the persistent exclusion of women from managerial roles not only reflects gender bias but also reinforces a media narrative that privileges male authority. Women in leadership positions often experience what is termed the “double bind,” where they are criticized for being too assertive or too soft in applying standards that are not equally applied to their male counterparts.

Edewor and Aluko (2007) highlighted that women in Nigerian media often face a "glass ceiling" an invisible but real barrier that prevents them from rising beyond a certain level, regardless of competence or experience. Emejulu and Adesanya (2020) stated that, Nigerian women journalists often struggle to balance work demands with expectations of domestic responsibilities. These expectations serve as justification for their exclusion from roles that require long hours, high visibility, or assertive leadership—traits that are stereotypically viewed as male. Moreover, the absence of mentorship and female role models in leadership positions further discourages young female journalists from aspiring to such roles. As noted by Ekeh and Ekeanyanwu (2013), mentorship is a critical factor in leadership development, yet many women in Nigerian media have few, if any, mentors to guide them through organizational hierarchies. This lack of support contributes to a cycle where the absence of women in leadership today makes it less likely for women to attain leadership in the future.

Recent global movements advocating for gender equity, such as the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Gender Equality), have drawn attention to these issues, prompting international and local media development organizations to call for reforms. However, progress has been slow. A 2020 report by the International Women’s Media Foundation (IWMF) indicates that although more women are entering the media profession, their representation in top leadership roles remains minimal, especially in Africa. This trend is reflected in NTA and AIT, where unreliable evidence and limited surveys suggest that few women occupy editorial or executive positions, and those who do often face resistance or skepticism as no woman has been Director-General of these organizations. Gendered perceptions affect how authority is assigned or denied in terms of professional identity. Female media leaders are often expected to over perform to be seen as equal to their male counterparts. In their work on leadership theory, Eagly and Carli (2007), argue that women face a “labyrinth” rather than a clear path to leadership. This metaphor captures the complex and nonlinear route that women must take, navigating institutionalized sexism, cultural expectations, and internalized doubt. Media organizations whether print, radio, television, or online, often compound, the effect of these stereotypes by limiting training opportunities and a lack of gender-sensitive workplace policies. For instance, there are no widespread policies on maternity leave, flexible schedules, or anti-harassment frameworks in many small or medium-sized media outlets. Consequently, talented women often drop out of the profession altogether or remain in subordinate roles, unable to break through the ceiling.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian media organization and its leadership structure, has been characterized with male domination over the years. Despite the increasing participation of female practitioners in the last few decades; their presence in leadership positions remains low. Since the establishment of the Nigerian Television Authority in 1958 (NTA) and Africa Independent Television (AIT) in 1996, a pattern of gender-based stereotypes has continue to limit the professional growth and leadership potential of women in media organizations. These stereotypes, which are often rooted in socio-cultural norms, institutional biases, and traditional gender expectations, portray women as less competent, less authoritative, or emotionally unqualified for leadership roles. As a result, many

qualified and experienced female journalists are overlooked for promotions, excluded from editorial decision-making processes, and confined to gendered or supportive roles that offer little room for advancement.

Leadership in media is not merely about occupying top positions; it significantly shapes the direction, tone, and priorities of media content and public discourse. However, media organizations often function within patriarchal frameworks that indirectly favor male dominance, both in newsroom culture and organizational hierarchy. These institutions rarely implement active policies to support gender equity or create leadership pipelines for women, thus strengthening a professional environment where leadership is associated with masculinity. Consequently, women are either discouraged from aspiring to leadership roles or are subjected to higher performance standards than their male counterparts to justify their positions.

1.3 Research questions

1. How does the stereotypic leadership model in NTA and AIT affects female media practitioner's the career advancement and professional development in Nigeria?
2. How do socio-cultural norms influence the perception of female media practitioners' appointment as Director-General in NTA and AIT?
3. What are the common leadership stereotypes faced by female media practitioners in NTA and AIT?

1.4 Study Objectives

1. To examine how stereotypic media leadership affect the career advancement and professional development of female media practitioners in the NTA and AIT.
2. To explore the influence of socio-cultural norms on the appointment of female journalists or practitioners as Director-General in NTA and AIT.
3. To identify the common leadership stereotypes encountered by female media practitioners in NTA and AIT.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study provides a new perspective on the persistent issue of gender-based leadership stereotypes that continue to marginalize female media practitioners in NTA and AIT. Despite the increasing number of women entering the media industry, their representation in leadership and decision-making roles remains excessively low. This study provides critical insight into the structural and social barriers that inhibit gender equity in media leadership by exploring the cultural, institutional, and professional dynamics that shape these stereotypes and proposes a new equitable model of leadership that promotes inclusivity.

First, the study will contribute to academic discourse by filling a gap in gender and media studies, particularly within the Nigerian and sub-national context. While much has been written about gender inequality in the workplace globally, limited studies have examined how leadership stereotypes manifest in specific cultural and institutional settings such as NTA and AIT. Thus, the findings will provide context-specific knowledge that can inform future research and theoretical development.

Second, by highlighting the real-life experiences and challenges faced by women in the industry, the study will be valuable to media practitioners and professionals. The research can encourage critical reflection among media managers, editors, and policy influencers by documenting these experiences, prompting them to re-evaluate workplace cultures and leadership pathways within their organizations. This could ultimately lead to more inclusive policies and practices that support gender diversity in leadership roles.

Third, the study will benefit policymakers and advocacy groups focused on gender equality and media reform. The evidence gathered will offer a strong empirical basis for developing policies and advocacy strategies aimed at dismantling institutionalized gender bias and promoting equal opportunities in the media sector. It will also

support efforts aligned with national and international goals, such as the Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Gender Equality), which calls for the elimination of discrimination in all forms.

Finally, this study will empower female media practitioners and aspiring journalists by acknowledging their struggles and amplifying their voices. Understanding specific stereotypes and systemic issues will help build awareness and resilience, while also encouraging women to pursue leadership positions despite societal and organizational resistance. The study may also inspire mentorship programs, training initiatives, and gender-sensitive reforms that support women's professional advancement in the media.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to provoke organizational change, inform policy, contribute to academic knowledge, and advance the cause of gender equity in media leadership across Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the study

This study focuses on exploring the issue of leadership stereotypes faced by female media practitioners in Nigeria's NTA and AIT. This study investigates the ways in which gender-based assumptions, patriarchal leadership construction, and biases impact women's access to participation in and, performance within leadership roles in media establishments. The research is concerned with how such stereotypes manifest in professional settings, how they influence decision-making roles, promotions, and job responsibilities, and how they contribute to the underrepresentation of women in top-tier media leadership positions.

Literature Review

The media's role in shaping and reshaping societal narratives and promoting democratic ideals is undeniably significant. However, the internal structures and power dynamics within media organizations especially NTA and AIT as foremost broadcast organizations in Nigeria, often reflect the same gender inequalities they are expected to reconstruct in society. As in many other professional sectors, media leadership to be male-dominated, and women often encounter systemic barriers (glass ceiling) that limit their upward mobility or career growth. One of the most pervasive of these barriers is the existence of stereotypic leadership model that is deeply rooted in patriarchal culturally conditioned beliefs that equate leadership qualities with traditionally masculine traits such as assertiveness, authority, and dominance.

Leadership or Media Management Concept

In this context, leadership is equated to management. This is a complex and multifaceted concept that involves staffing, organizing, directing, controlling, supervising, influencing, guiding and motivating individuals or teams to achieve specific goals. Drucker, (1978) viewed management as the art of getting things done through others (Hersey et al., 2013; Northouse, 2016; Olayisade & Olawumi, 2021). Effective leadership involves a combination of skills, traits, and behaviors that inspire and motivate followers to achieve organizational goals (Bass, 1985; Kouzes & Posner, 2017; Conger & Kanungo, 1998). Gender disparity in media leadership refers to the unequal representation of men and women in high-level positions within media organizations. This includes editors-in-chief, news directors, managing editors, and media executives. Despite the progress made in promoting gender equality across many sectors, leadership in the media industry remains dominated by men, both globally and Nigeria. Gender disparity in media leadership is a pervasive issue that affects media organizations worldwide. Despite significant development toward gender equality in various sectors, the media industry continues to exhibit a pronounced gender imbalance, particularly in leadership roles. This disparity not only influences organizational dynamics but also shapes the content produced, impacting public perception and societal norms.

Globally, studies have shown a persistent gap. A 2022 report by WAN-IFRA Women in News found that women held only 10% and 31% of business and editorial leadership roles in major media houses across 17

countries, respectively. Two years later, in 2024, the percentage increased slightly, with women holding 24% of leadership roles overall. However, this still highlights a major imbalance as, men continue to dominate top media positions. In the United States, a 2023 study by the Reuters Institute showed that women made up only 22% of top editorial roles in major news organizations across 12 countries, indicating that this issue is not limited to any one region.

In the UK, the gender gap in the media is also alarming. A 2024 report called *Re-Framing the Picture* analyzed over 12,000 films and found that men held 78% of all key creative roles. The study concluded that if the current trend continues, the UK film industry might not reach gender parity until 2085. This lack of women in leadership affects not only workplace equity but also the type of content that is created, often resulting in a lack of female voices and stories in the media.

The situation in Nigeria is equally troubling. A 2024 study by the Wole Soyinka Center for Investigative Journalism (WSCIJ) found that women held only 25.7% of the leadership positions in 111 Nigerian media outlets. The representation was especially low in print (4.6%) and online platforms (5.5%), while radio and television showed slightly better figures. The same study found that women were not only underrepresented in leadership but also in the news itself. Only 24% of news anchors and authors were women, and only 7.1% of news content focused on women's issues.

Scholars have studied these trends and provided insights into why the gap persists. Doris Ruth Eikhof, a leading expert on gender and the creative industries, stresses that merely increasing the number of women in media is not enough—putting women in influential, decision-making roles is important. She argues for policies that include real accountability and industry-wide reforms, such as quotas and funding incentives, to support female leadership Oliveira & Huang, 2025.

Eddy and Arguedas (2023) pointed out that even though more women are entering journalism, they are not reaching top editorial positions. This indicates that the problem is not only about recruitment but also about deeper structural barriers within media organizations. These include gender bias, lack of mentorship, unequal access to career advancement opportunities, and workplace cultures that discourage women from rising to top or Directorate-General positions.

The impact of gender disparity in media leadership transcends office politics. It influences how stories are told and whose voices are heard. Media has the power to shape public opinion, and when leadership is not diverse, it often leads to content that reflects only a narrow segment of society. For example, Fafowora (2020) highlighted how Nigeria's media often portrays women in politics in stereotypical and negative ways, which discourages public support for female leaders.

These dynamics are deeply entrenched in Nigeria. Adam (2019) studied women's leadership in government-owned media organizations in Niger State and found that patriarchal norms and workplace culture often hinder women's progress. The study revealed that leadership was widely viewed as a "male preserve," and women who aspired to such positions were sometimes seen as overambitious or disrespectful to traditional gender roles. Many female journalists reported feeling that they had to work "twice as hard" to earn the same respect as their male counterparts.

The belief that leadership is a masculine trait is at the heart of the issue. According to Eikhof (2024), such gender-coded leadership expectations contribute to a "chilly climate" that deters female media practitioners from rising to senior roles.

Empirical Review

Gündemir, et. al. (2022) used natural language processing to analyze how appointing women to senior leadership roles impacts organizational language. The findings indicate that increased female representation in leadership positions leads to a shift in language, associating women more with agential traits essential for leadership success. This language change reflects a broader cultural shift toward gender inclusivity in organizational settings.

Diego and Huang (2025) analyzed data from over 62,000 papers across 121 communication journals to assess gender disparities in academic recognition and compensation. The research revealed that female authors are underrepresented, receive fewer citations, and earn lower salaries, particularly at the assistant professor level. These disparities highlighted systemic biases that can hinder women's progression into leadership roles within media organizations, emphasizing the need for policies that promote equity in recognition and compensation.

Feenstra, et al. (2023) investigated the evolution of managerial stereotypes in the Netherlands over a period of 15 years. By analyzing data from 5,542 Dutch employees in 2005, 2010, and 2020, the researchers found a decreasing preference for traditionally masculine leadership traits and an increasing appreciation for feminine traits. Despite this shift, masculine traits remained more favored overall. The study indicated that while perceptions are changing, the stereotype of the "ideal manager" still leans toward masculine characteristics, posing challenges for women aspiring to leadership roles in media organizations.

Boatright-Horowitz and Goodman (2017) examined how organizational practices in media firms influence the perception of female leadership. The authors found that women in media organizations are often judged more harshly than their male counterparts, especially when they take on leadership roles. Women in leadership positions are also more likely to face challenges in balancing their leadership style with societal expectations of femininity. This study is particularly relevant to this current research, where traditional gender norms may affect the career trajectories of female media practitioners and hinder their advancement to leadership positions in both NTA and AIT.

Schein and Mueller (2017) and Aina (2012) addressed the role of gender stereotypes in media leadership positions. Despite the increasing presence of women in the media industry, leadership roles are still predominantly held by men. This study explores how gender stereotypes, such as the association of leadership with masculinity, affect female leaders' opportunities and perceptions in the media. This study is particularly relevant to NTA and AIT, where the intersection of traditional gender roles and the media industry may limit women's leadership potential.

Theoretical Framework

The Glass Ceiling Theory

The Glass Ceiling Theory, coined by Marilyn Loden in 1978, suggests that, despite their qualifications or capabilities, women and minorities face invisible barriers that prevent them from advancing to the highest levels of leadership within an organization. These barriers often exist not because of overt discrimination but because of systemic issues within organizational culture, policies, structures, and practices (Asemah, et al., 2017). The glass ceiling is "transparent" in the sense that women can see the leadership positions above them but are often unable to reach them due to both institutional and societal forces that constrain their advancement. This theory highlights the subtle yet powerful ways in which gender inequality is perpetuated in the media industry (Federal Glass Ceiling, 1995; IWWMF, 2020; GMMP, 2020). Women may find themselves stuck in lower or mid-level positions despite, being equally or more qualified than their male colleagues. Institutional factors, such as biased hiring practices, unequal access to professional development opportunities, and the reinforcement of stereotypical views about women's leadership abilities, all contribute to the glass ceiling.

Women may also face personal barriers, such as a lack of mentorship or networking opportunities, which can limit their ability to break through these invisible barriers (Baker, 2021; Brugnoli & Delmastro, 2022). The glass ceiling also impacts not only hiring and promotions but also, the representation of women in leadership roles in the media, with far fewer women in executive and decision-making positions than their male counterparts.

Social Role Theory (Eagly, 1987)

Social Role Theory argues that differences in male and female behavior arise from the expectations associated with their roles in society. According to this theory, men and women are socialized into different roles based on historically constructed social norms (Eagly & Karau, 2002). Men are expected to occupy roles that require agency, assertiveness, and control, which align with traits such as decisiveness and authority that are often valued in leadership (Crenshaw, 1989; Edewor, 2014). Women are associated with nurturing, empathy, and communal roles, which are seen as incompatible with leadership characteristics. This incongruity between the societal expectations of women and the qualities needed for leadership positions creates a bias against women who wish to occupy leadership roles in media organizations. Social Role Theory explains why female media practitioners may be stereotyped as less competent or authoritative than their male counterparts when seeking leadership positions. This theory argues that the traditional expectations of women to be nurturing and supportive conflict with the expectations of leaders to be commanding and decisive, which may prevent women from being promoted or even considered for leadership positions (Haegel, 2024; Kauter, 1977). It also explains why female practitioners might face resistance when they display leadership associated-behaviors, such as assertiveness or independence, since these behaviors are seen as "unfeminine."

Methods

The study adopted the survey research method. Survey method of research is used to describe or explain a situation, hence descriptive and analytical methods. This study adopted an analytical method to analyze, "the glass ceiling and stereotypic leadership style in NTA and AIT in Nigeria."

Research Design

The researcher adopted the quantitative method of data collection for this study. Adejoh et al., (2025), Allen, et al (2016), Falaye and Okwilagwe (2016) and Anyaegbu, et al (2016), adopted this design and generated the desired data.

Population of the study

The population comprised all management staff from managerial to directorate cadres in NTA and AIT. To ensure that those, who are directly affected or have experienced unfair treatment in their appointments or promotions are selected for this study

Samples Size

The sample size of this study comprised all women within the managerial and directorate cadres in NTA and AIT. Twenty (20) women who were willing to participate in the study were administered the questionnaire.

Sampling techniques

Stratify and available sampling techniques were adopted to ensure that the right people (women) who were within the managerial cadre and above and were willing to participate in the study, were, selected.

Research instruments

This study adopted a structured questionnaire as the data generation instrument. The questions were structured to generate quantitative data using a modified likert scale of; SA, A, D and SD.

Validity of the instrument

The instrument was validated based on content by, senior academics (content validity). A language expert also validated the instruments to ascertain face (construct validity) in ensuring the “fit-for-use”, so that what, is meant is what is communicated, what is understood generates the desired response or data.

The reliability of the instrument

To ensure the instrument’s repeatability, pilot test was carried on 4 respondents (which constitute 20% of the sample) among lower cadre female employees in NTA and AIT who were not eligible to participate in the main study. Cronbach’s alpha was used to analyze the data and a reliability index of 0.86 was obtained. The instrument was adjudged to be reliable because the reliability index stands above 0.5 to positive one (1). This agrees with Abbas’ (2009) statement that a reliability index close to one (1) is reliable.

Location of the study

The study was conducted at the NTA Headquarters, Garki area 11, and the Abuja office of AIT, Kpaduma Hill, Asokoro extension, Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Administration of research instrument and data gathering

After the instrument was validated and pilot tested, it was administered by the researcher through an online Google form with the aid of a program developer who designed a link using survey monkey. The link was sent to the targeted respondents through their career platforms, and the responses of those who were willing to participate in the study were collected.

Procedure for Data Presentation and Analysis

The data collected through the structured questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. All objectives were tested using regression analysis.

The mean of the scale was 2.5. Decision mean scores equaled to or above 2.5 were considered “Agreed” whereas those below 2.5 were regarded as “Disagreed”. The descriptive and inferential analyses of each of the three research questions are presented as follows:

Results

Table 1: How does the stereotypic media leadership model in NTA and AIT affects female media practitioners’ career advancement and professional development in Nigeria?

S/N	Item statement	mean	SD	Decision
1	Stereotypic leadership inhibits women from aspiring to their career peak	3.19	0.70	Accepted
2	Stereotypic leadership often denies women the opportunities to become Director-General even when they are the most qualified	3.13	0.70	Accepted
3	Stereotypic leadership reduces women to supportive or agency roles	3.50	0.55	Accepted
4	Stereotypic leadership often neglects women as incapable of handling top managerial responsibilities	3.32	0.78	Accepted
5	Stereotypic leadership instills feelings of inferiority, self-withdrawal, and lack of participation in the workplace	3.50	0.55	Accepted

The table above shows the cumulative mean of 16.64 and SD of 3.28. The standard deviation of 3.28 is smaller and close to the cumulative mean, indicating that a larger number of respondents agreed with the statements. The mean of 16.64 is greater than the decision mean of 3.28. This result implies that the

stereotypic leadership style often denied women opportunities to become Director-General in NTA and AIT even when they were the most qualified.

Table 2: How do socio-cultural norms influence the appointment of female media practitioners as director-general in NTA and AIT?

S/N.	Item statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1	NTA and AIT Workplace policies often reflect socio-cultural norms that view women as only good in domestic roles.	3.50	0.55	Accepted
2	Women are seen as incapable of occupying top leadership positions because of their socio-cultural beliefs	3.17	0.51	Accepted
3	African socio-cultural norms, discourage women from aspiring to the top of their careers	2.71	1.41	Accepted
4	Women are often seen as belonging to the kitchen and the “other room.”	3.13	0.70	Accepted
5	These socio-cultural practices negate equity and fair play in workplace politics.	3.05	0.53	Accepted

Table 2 shows an average mean of 15.02 and std. dev. of 3.7. The SD of 3.7 is smaller and close to the average mean, indicating that larger number of respondents agreed with the statement. Consequently, workplace policies in NTA and AIT often reflect socio-cultural norms that view women as only good in domestic, agency subordinate roles, thereby inhibiting women from aspiring to the peak of their careers.

Table 3: Common leadership stereotypes faced by female media practitioners in NTA and AIT

S/N	Item statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Women are often considered for promotion or appointment to top media leadership positions	2.07	0.70	Rejected
2	Women are rarely sexually harassed for appointment or promotion.	1.98	0.85	Rejected
3	There is no bias against women, and appointments are based on merit.	2.41	0.74	Rejected
4	Women naturally prefer to be led, rather than to lead in an organization.	2.18	2.10	Rejected
5	Women are not assertive but, weak and compromising	1.50	0.55	Rejected

The table above revealed a cumulative mean score of 10.14 and the standard deviation score of 4.94. The SD obtained was, lower than the decision mean of 10.14. This indicates that a larger number of respondents disagreed with the statements. The mean 10.14. is higher than the decision mean of 2.5. Therefore, the respondents largely rejected the statements that women are often considered for promotion or appointment to the top media leadership position, are rarely sexually harassed for appointment or promotion, or that women naturally prefer to be led rather, than to lead in an organization.

Conclusion

Gender disparity in media leadership is a major issue that continues to affect the quality and diversity of media content around the world. Although some progress has been made, the pace is slow and uneven. Closing this

gap requires not only individual effort but also collective action from media institutions, policymakers, and society at large. Giving women fair space at the top in media organizations is not only a matter of justice but also essential for a media landscape that is balanced, inclusive and representative.

Recommendation

Several actions have been recommended to fix this imbalance. These include enforcing gender equity policies in media companies, offering women leadership training programs, and creating mentorship opportunities. In addition, media organizations should review their recruitment and promotion practices to ensure fairness and transparency in compliance with AFA. Governments and media regulators can also play a role by introducing policies that support leadership diversity and inclusivity.

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